

Controversial issues in biology: Impacts of microplastics in marine food webs

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General introduction

This is the third blog post written by students from the Controversial Issues in Biology (BIOL 700) class of Fall 2024, during which we explored eight controversial issues, centered in biology, proposed by DBS faculty. For each topic, a pair of students selected and read seven pro and seven contra papers, summarized key points, and posed clarifying questions for another pair to review. The second pair then presented their comprehensive review to the class, followed by a full-class discussion and a vote on a scale of 1 to 10, with 1 indicating strong opposition to the controversial issue and 10 representing full support. In this blog post, we synthesize the information from the papers and peer feedback on the impacts of microplastics in marine food webs.

What are microplastics, and what constitutes their introduction into the marine food web?

Microplastics (MPs) are a general term for extremely small plastics, from the point of being invisible to the naked eye at 1000 μm up to those that are 5 mm. They are most often produced from the fragmentation of macroplastics due to UV or physical damage to these macroplastics, and in this case, the fragments have entered marine environments and therefore can be present in marine food webs. Among the con-papers, 5 identified MPs as being less than 5 mm in size (Carbery et al., 2018; Carlin et al., 2020; Horn et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2019; Zhang et al., 2019). Other papers provide a range of accepted sizes, such as Setälä et al. proposing a range of 10 - 220 μm in diameter (Setälä et al., 2014) and Goss et al. giving a range of 1 mm to 500 μm (Goss et al., 2018). Gutow et al., 2016 gave no defined size of MPs but

did indicate that the tests performed in the paper were done with beads of 10 µm in diameter (Gutow et al., 2016). All papers discuss ingestion as the vector that transfers MPs from one substrate to another, but there is a range of vectors that the papers discuss. In terms of ingestion, some papers cite a more pelagic style of microplastic transfer where free-floating particles become ingested by zooplankton, fish, and the gills of shellfish, with plastics often found primarily in the gastrointestinal tracts of these species (Setälä et al., 2014; Zhang et al., 2019). Moving from pelagic to fixed microplastic particles, other papers detailed the prevalence of MPs in/on marine flora such as seagrass and seaweeds. Here, the vector moves from pelagic MPs into marine flora, which is then consumed by herbivorous marine species such as parrotfish and periwinkles, thus ingesting and moving MPs along in the food web (Goss et al., 2018; Gutow et al., 2016). Other papers discuss the transitions between terrestrial and aquatic MPs through species such as birds and crabs, both of which spend time in and out of the ocean, and were seen to contain MPs in their GI tracts as well (Carlin et al., 2020; Horn et al., 2019). The exact point source of where these species ingest the MPs is not known due to both crabs and birds feeding on land and in the sea, allowing vectors of MPs in food webs from terrestrial habitats directly to aquatic through a species or vice versa from sea to land. Two papers discussed the human impact of the consumption of contaminated marine species from producer to consumer (phytoplankton to human). These papers discuss bioaccumulation and biomagnification of MPs through these trophic levels, and how humans can consume them at many points, for instance, with mussels and tuna. The papers also note the absence of thorough toxicological testing that has been done on marine species as they relate to human consumption, and that we do not fully understand how marine MPs in the food web truly affect us (Carbery et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2019).

What are the pros?

MPs have been discovered in the marine ecosystem and even inside marine organisms. These MPs come in variations from the different sizes and types of plastic they are made from (Rodríguez

Torres et al., 2023) proposed characterizing MPs not just as a size range between 1 and 1000 μm , but also on solid state, shape, color, origin, and chemical composition. The effects of these MPs are mainly looked at as a negative effect on the marine ecosystem, but some articles prove otherwise. The majority of the pro-papers consisted of lab settings where the microplastic influence was controlled, making the impact of MPs not as accurate as it would be in a wild marine ecosystem (Scott et al., 2019). Other articles portray the idea that MPs do not have any effect due to their small sizes and plastic types. For example, polyethylene is a thermoplastic polymer commonly used in plastic production. It has been discussed that we don't even know if MPs with a diameter of less than 1 μm can even be absorbed by marine life (Catarino & Henry, 2018). If these MPs are not appreciably absorbed, their potential to accumulate in tissues and cause problems is very low (Catarino & Henry, 2018). In conclusion, these potential "pros" are interesting to consider; it is important to remember that the negative impacts of MPs in marine ecosystems, including ingestion by marine organisms, toxicity, bioaccumulation, and ecosystem disruption, are far more significant and widespread.

What are the cons?

MPs are found in all marine organisms throughout the food web, from microscopic plankton to large fish marine plants, and algae. These plastics are often found in the stomach and or digestive tracts of these organisms and on the surfaces of marine flora. The toxicological effects of leaching microplastic chemicals are largely unknown and likely enter humans via the consumption of marine species. All con papers found MPs present in their studies/reviews from rates of 30% of samples containing them and up to 100% (Foley et al., 2018; Jacob et al., 2019; Jemec Kokalj et al., 2019; McCormick et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2019). Likely all marine organism species are affected due to the sheer abundance of MPs in the water column, and the high encounter rate these organisms will have with these small particles. Seeing zooplankton ingest MPs both directly and indirectly (Setälä et al., 2014) gives scope to how trophic transfer can start in the smallest form and rise through the food web. Marine flora are also seen to

accumulate MPs with their large surface area (Goss et al., 2018; Gutow et al., 2016) and pass them up into the food web via fish herbivory. Species such as birds of prey move MPs through the marine food web, connecting terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems and bringing MPs to and from both (Carlin et al., 2020). The effect humans have experienced from marine organism consumption is still largely unstudied regarding the direct transfer of marine substances to human consumption. Other factors, such as toxicity from broken-down polymers that have biomagnified into organisms like fish or shellfish, also remain underexplored (Carbery et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2019). Overall, the cons of marine MPs are numerous and present a large frontier of research to be conducted to determine the lasting effects of plastic contamination in the marine environment.

Table 1. Pros and cons of microplastics in marine food webs

Cons of Marine MPs: Major Themes	Source and Student Review	Pros of Marine MPs: Major Themes	Source and Student Review
<p>Pelagic Microplastic Ingestion:</p> <p>Microplastic particle ingestion is often seen to occur from pelagic particles entering organisms through normal feeding and respiration processes.</p>	<p>Setälä et al. 2013</p> <p>Zhang et al. 2019</p>	<p>Microplastic ingestion has a small impact:</p> <p>MPs that are discovered to be a certain size do not affect marine life.</p>	<p>Rodríguez Torres et al. 2022</p> <p>Jacob et al 2019</p>

<p>Marine Flora as an Ingestion Vector:</p> <p>MPs are seen to accumulate on marine flora in the water column and enter the food web through marine herbivores consuming this flora.</p>	<p>Gutow et al. 2019</p> <p>Goss et al. 2018</p>	<p>Microplastic effects on marine life have been tested:</p> <p>MPs are seen to have no negative effects on marine life when the amount of plastic is the controlled variable in the test.</p>	<p>Mateos-Cárdenas et al 2019</p> <p>Zhu et al. 2024</p>
<p>Ingestion from species that inhabit both terrestrial and aquatic habitats:</p> <p>Species such as crabs and birds have been observed to have ingested MPs in their GI tracts, blurring the line of where MPs enter marine food webs, either terrestrial or aquatic.</p>	<p>Carlin et al. 2020</p> <p>Horn et al. 2018</p>	<p>Primary MPs versus aged are studied to portray the difference in ecotoxicity:</p> <p>Current studies show an understanding of how the environmental aging of MPs shows that their ecotoxicity becomes lower as they get older.</p>	<p>Foley et al. 2018</p> <p>Jemec Kokalj et al. 2019</p>

<p>The effects of MPs in marine Food Webs on humans:</p> <p>The effects of bioaccumulation, biomagnification, and toxicity of marine MPs on humans (via consumption of marine organisms) are largely unknown and require further study.</p>	<p>Wang et al. 2019</p> <p>Carbery et al. 2018</p>	<p>The effects of MPs on the reproduction of marine fish:</p> <p>The effects of periodic consumption on a tropical marine fish, and there were no visible effects on the internal organs of the fish.</p>	<p>McCormisk et al 2023</p> <p>Catarino and Henry 2018</p>
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What do we think?

An average relevance vote of 5.33 (on a 1-10 scale) gives the topic a fair level of concern, with a range of the votes being 1, with only votes of scores 5 and 6 being seen. With non-polarizing and consistent voting results, the issue presents as important and less controversial than others reviewed in the class. Plastics are a highly contemporary issue globally, and the ocean is just one example of that, with vectors of microplastic transport in marine ecosystems being highly varied and numerous. We find this topic to be highly relevant, due to the multi-factorial effects that MPs pose, not only to the detriment of marine ecosystems but to us humans who at times end up consuming MPs that have been concentrated into an organism. It is also important to note that microplastic concentration appears at high frequencies

even at lower trophic levels (such as shellfish like mussels and crabs) presenting a risk to us as consumers at every instance of marine organism consumption.

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